

FLOW Campaign - Multi-lidar coherence measurements of offshore turbulent inflows

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Motivation

- Wind turbines are getting ever larger (i.e. taller) – now over 300m tip height
- Design load calculations utilize turbulence models as defined in IEC standards:

IEC 61400-1:2019 © IEC 2019 – 43 –

Table 2 – Design load cases (DLC)

Design situation	DLC	Wind condition	Other conditions	Type of analysis	Partial safety factors
1) Power production	1.1	NTM $V_{in} < V_{hub} < V_{out}$	For extrapolation of extreme events	U	N
	1.2	NTM $V_{in} < V_{hub} < V_{out}$		F	*
	1.3	ETM $V_{in} < V_{hub} < V_{out}$		U	N
	1.4	ECD $V_{hub} = V_r - 2 \text{ m/s}, V_r, V_r + 2 \text{ m/s}$		U	N
	1.5	EWS $V_{in} < V_{hub} < V_{out}$		U	N

Two turbulence models are given here for design load calculations. The turbulent velocity fluctuations are assumed to be a stationary, random vector field whose components have zero-mean Gaussian statistics. The first model is recommended.

- 1) Mann uniform shear model.
- 2) Kaimal spectral and exponential coherence model.

- We have very few observations of the spatial structure of offshore turbulence at the heights turbines are now operating
- The turbulence models have not yet been validated for this use
- Assumptions in the models may be violated above the surface layer (e.g. meso/microscale spectral gap)

FLOW: Atmospheric Flow, Loads and pOwer for Wind energy

- Joint European project, €6MM budget, 4-years long
- Objectives:
 - Develop new engineering models parametrizing wind physics and turbulence at higher altitudes.
 - Predict, through models, the production and loads of modern GW-scale and 400-m tall wind energy systems with high confidence both onshore and offshore.
 - Validate the models with an unprecedented amount of data, reduce the errors of the predictions, and quantify the uncertainty.

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FLOW experiment location

FLOW experiment

- Equipment:
 - 2x Lumibird Streamline XR+
 - 2x DTU Long-Range WindScanner
 - 1x Vaisala Windcube 200S
 - 1x Vaisala CL31
 - 2x monitoring cameras

Lidar scan configuration

- All lidars set to staring (LOS) mode, 2Hz sampling
- 6 dual-Doppler crossing points on (near) horizontal plane
- 2-component wind vector retrieved at each crossing point
- Lateral coherence computed between points
- Phase 1 intersection plane at 150m above sea surface
- Phase 2 increased to 250m

Courtesy: Jakob Mann, DTU Wind

Why should we trust these measurements?

1. Pre-campaign calibrations of LOS speed and range (against met-mast and between lidar pairs)
2. Hard-target mapping throughout campaign
3. LOS inter-comparisons
4. Sea surface levelling (RHI)
5. Drone beam alignment

2

1

3

Brise vs Storm at 700.5m
No. of points: 1687

4

4

Drone + lidar data analysis

Selected result

- Coherence measurements at different separation distances compared against a new improved turbulence model [1] with improved performance for low-frequency wind fluctuations

$\alpha\varepsilon = 0.027$, $L = 288.4\text{m}$, $\Gamma = 1.308$, $\theta = 301.3$, $U = 6.93\text{m/s}$, Stability = VVU, $c = 8\text{e-}05$, $\psi = 37.8$, $ht = 250\text{m}$

Solid lines: observations. Dashed lines: model
 Left: along wind component, Right: cross wind component.
 Stability: Very unstable

Courtesy: Ansh Patel, DTU Wind

[1] Syed AH, Mann J. A model for low-frequency, anisotropic wind fluctuations and coherences in the marine atmosphere. *Boundary-Layer Meteorology*. 2024 Jan;190(1):1.

More information

- Website including publications: <http://flow-horizon.eu>
- Dataset is freely available:
 - Patel, Ansh; Simon, Elliot; Mann, Jakob; Sjöholm, Mikael; Rolighed Thorsen, Gunhild; Hung, Lin-ya; et al. (2025). Trans experiment (FLOW) - raw lidar data. Technical University of Denmark. Dataset. <https://doi.org/10.11583/DTU.28749252.v1>
- Journal papers forthcoming:
 - An experimental campaign to measure turbulence in the marine boundary layer
 - Lidar observations of turbulence for tall offshore wind turbines
 - Using drone hard-targeting for improved scanning wind lidar beam pointing accuracy